

Self-Objectification, Colorism, and Social Appearance Anxiety in Youth

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Abstract

The present study aimed to inquire into the relationship between self-objectification (SO), colorism, and social appearance anxiety (SAA) in youth. It also intended to find out the predictors for SAA and to explore gender differences. The number of participants in this study was (N = 243) with an age range from 15-25 years. The sample consisted of 122 female participants and 121 male participants. The research design used in this study was correlational. A purposive and snowball sampling strategy was used for sample recruitment. The tools used in this study to collect the data were Social Appearance Anxiety Scale (Hart et al., 2008), Self-Objectification Questionnaire (Noll & Fredrickson, 1998), and the In-Group Colorism Scale (Harvey, Tenniel, & Banks, 2017). The statistical analysis used in this study was Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Linear Regression, Independent Sample T-Test, and ANOVA. The findings of the Pearson correlation showed that there is a significant positive correlation between colorism and SAA and also between SO and SAA. The regression analysis showed that colorism and SO positively predict SAA. The T-test analysis revealed that the rate of SO, colorism, and SAA were higher in females than males; and in unmarried than married youth. Results of ANOVA revealed significant mean differences in socioeconomic status and residential area on SAA. This study adds to the literature on SO, colorism and SAA, and it is the first research that is conducted to investigate the impact of SO and colorism on SAA among Pakistani youth. These issues trigger psychological problems so this study will assess the effect of these variables on the mental health of individuals and help researchers to formulate an intervention or counseling plan regarding these issues.

Introduction

Self-objectification and Colorism

Self-objectification is defined as a persistent appearance of the objectification of women is the men gaze, which was first named a women's activist film scholar Mulvey in 1975 to portray the manner by which ladies were seen in sexual manner to be taken a glance at and epitomize by male gaze (Vandermassen, 2011). So is seeing one's self as an object without considering any thoughts, feelings, or mortality (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997) Females are more prone to objectify than males, especially in male-centric societies (Vangeel et al., 2018). In particular, self-objectification prompts higher body disgrace, lack of confidence (Choma et al., 2010), anxiety, eating disturbances (Tiggemann & Williams, 2012), depression, and sexual problems (Szymanski et al., 2011). It also contrarily impacts the cognitive performance of women (Fredrickson et al., 1998). It was also found that SO is associated with SAA (Miner et al., 2002).

Women of dark colors are normally depicted as forceful, tyrannical, and unfeminine, while women of lighter skin shades are depicted as delicate and physically intriguing (Collins, 2000). Cultural factors, frequently present in the media, are the most compelling components that drive females to strive for flawlessness (Stokes et al., 2016). Meier & Grey (2014) found that higher appearance disclosure on Facebook use was highly related to motivation for slimness, weight dissatisfaction, the internalization of the thin ideal and SO. Fox & colleagues (2021) found that selfie-takers showed higher SO, a more negative state of mind reduced confidence. According to Roca (2018), females utilized filter more to improve or alter the quality of their skin in pictures.

Prejudice against people with more dark complexions is called colorism or also shade-ism which is a term authored by Alice Walker during the 1980s. Colorism is more secretive and "disguised underneath the still waters of social manners" (Williams, 2002, p. 8). It is associated with the shape and color of the eyes, color, the length and texture of hair, and the shape and size of the nose and mouth (Maddox & Chase, 2004). Colonization and colorism are firmly knotted since the commencement of the world. In the subcontinent, the countries like Pakistan, India, and Bangladesh are yet encountering substantial impacts of colonization even after 70 years. Colorism in Pakistan has been ingrained so profoundly into our underlying foundations that we scarcely notice it. It has played a crucial part in creating certain mentalities towards beauty since the subjugation up to current

times. The fixation on light complexion is an undeniable and normal issue not just in Pakistan and India, but also in other Asian nations too (Hashmi, 2018).

Colorism has become a huge factor in the selection of a spouse (Glenn, 2008). Dark-skinned females are continually recommended to take brightening facials or medicines, and fairness creams (Raza, 2020). Burns (2021) stated that colorism influences the lives of dark persons significantly. According to Elves (2019), colorism affects how females of different skin tones are seen and it can straightforwardly affect their confidence levels. Women with fair skin felt more cherished in their relationships as compared to women of darker skin tones (Mathews, 2013). One study claims that the whole of Pakistani society is only concerned about women's modesty (Mumtaz & Shaheed, 1987). Even our media today portray dark-skinned people in an evil light, whereas the ones with lighter tones play the main character (Erin et al., 2018). Social media has surely influenced sustaining colorist standards. Filters make our skin look a lot fairer which is none less than digital colorists.

Social Anxiety in Youth

The concept of SAA was first introduced by Hart, Rejeski & Leary in 1989 and was characterized as the anxiety that individuals experience in light of others' assessments regarding their appearances (Hart et al., 1989). Boadi (2017) found a negative relationship between skin color gratification and SAA. Social appearance anxiety incorporates considerations (e.g., unreasonable tensions) and practices (e.g., appearance checking and disguising) comparable to appearance that can meddle with day by day life (Zimmer-Gembeck et al., 2018; Ghani et al., 2022). Consequently, youngsters may contrast themselves with pictures that are presented of optimistic and idealistic nature, which may provoke unreal assumptions for themselves and thusly produce more stress, body dissatisfaction, oversensitive behavior towards appearance related taunts and judgments and lack of confidence when these assumptions can't be met (Tiggemann and Zinoviev, 2019). Studies shown that teenagers with social appearance anxiety tend to overestimate their appearance more anxiously, belittle the nature of their own social appearance (Clark, 2001; khattak et al., 2021).

Social appearance anxiety is also associated with more elevated levels of psychological, behavioral and interpersonal issues (Claes et al., 2012) lack of adjustment levels and lack of life satisfaction levels (Bender et al., 2012), depression, substance abuse problems, and various types of anxiety in young age (Essau et al., 2014). Furthermore, both perfectionistic self-tendencies and appearance anxiety relate to one's external presentation, which is also similar to eating disorders since people with disturbed eating habits typically experience anxiety in regards to their appearance (Paxton, 2002). Munawar (2014) in his study found a negative connection between body image and social anxiety which means that social anxiety was higher in number in those who weren't satisfied with their body image. Moreover, it also showed that social anxiety and body image predicted aggression.

SAA is associated with more elevated levels of psychological, behavioral, and interpersonal issues (Claes et al., 2012), lack of adjustment levels & life dissatisfaction (Bender et al., 2012), depression, substance abuse, and various types of anxiety in young age (Essau et al., 2014). self-esteem (Argon, 2014), body dissatisfaction (Levinson & Rodebaugh, 2014), eating disorders (Levinson et al., 2013; Ahmad et al., 2022), not to mention aggravation, shuddering, perspiring, and speech errors (APA, 2000).

The Current Study

The present study aimed to explore the relationship between self-objectification, colorism and social appearance anxiety among youth in Pakistan. Colorism is a worldwide issue not just mere color (White, black or brown) issue, that has arisen into a powerful force separating individuals from individuals and, thusly, individuals from their own self. Likewise Self-objectification can be characterized as seeing oneself from a third person viewpoint that gets internalize into their own self. This viewpoint can prompt day

by day body observing and checking, which enhances the probability of body shame and level of anxiety which then enable social appearance anxiety which is the fear that one will be adversely assessed for their appearance. It was hypothesized that 1) there will be a significant positive relationship between colorism and social appearance anxiety 2) There will be a significant positive relationship between self-objectification and social appearance anxiety 3) Colorism will likely predict social appearance anxiety in youth 4) Self-objectification will likely predict social appearance anxiety in youth 5) It is likely to be that female youth will have more self-objectification, colorism, and social appearance anxiety as compared to male youth and 5) It is likely to be that unmarried youth will have more self-objectification, colorism, and social appearance anxiety as compared.

Method

Participants and Design

The research design used in this study was correlational. A purposive and snowball sampling strategy was used for sample recruitment. The sample was taken from schools, colleges, and universities in Lahore. The number of samples essential for the study was determined by an a priori power analysis (Gpower, Faul & Erfelder, 1992). A total of 243 participants were used in the data analysis. The sample consisted of 122 female participants and 121 male participants ranging from 15 years to 25 years of age. The sample included literate youth above 14

years and younger than 26 years who have either experienced SAA or any sort of discrimination based on their skin tone. Disabled population and International students were excluded. Pearson correlation analysis, Independent sample T-test, Linear Regression, and ANOVA were used as statistical analyses. Results were analyzed using SPSS-21.

Instruments

Social Appearance Anxiety Scale

SAAS is a self-report five-point scale that is comprised of 16 items in total from which only Item 1 requires inverse coding. This scale was developed to assess anxiety about being adversely assessed by others (Hart et al., 2008).

Self-Objectification Questionnaire (SOQ)

The SOQ is comprised of ten unique body trait items which are ranked in order. Five items are based on competence 1, 2, 4, 7, and 9, and the other five items are based on appearance traits 3, 5, 6, 8, and 10. Scores may lie under - 25 to 25 (Noll & Fredrickson, 1998).

In-Group Colorism Scale

The IGCS comprises five subscales with a total of 20 items utilizing a 7-point Likert scale design. It was created to measure how much skin color is significant across five fundamental aspects including Affiliation (9-12), Self-Concept (1-4), Attraction (13-16), Upward Mobility (17-20), and Impression Formation 5-8 (Harvey, Tennill, & Banks, 2017).

Procedure

First of all, formal permission was taken from the university and authors to start the data collection. The participants were approached online and were briefed about the aims of the current research. A consent form was prepared to obtain an individual's acceptance to participate in the study. It was clarified that information gathered from the participants would be used only for research purposes. In the end, participants were thanked for their cooperation. On average, it took 8 to 10 minutes for every participant to complete the survey. All the ethical guidelines were followed while completing the questionnaires and no rules were violated.

Ethical considerations

Participants were informed about the purpose and aim of the study. They were provided with informed consent in which they were told that they were participating in the research voluntarily and could withdraw from the study anytime they wanted to. Individuals were told that all demographics obtained were to be used for research purposes only. They were told that all information they were provided will be kept private and confidential and will not be communicated to any other person without their permission. Students were told that they were ethically obliged to behave appropriately during research by not lying, cheating, faking, or engaging in any other mischief.

Results

Table 1

Pearson Correlation among Self-Objectification, Colorism and Social Appearance Anxiety (N = 243)

Variables	1	2	3
1- Colorism	1	.50**	.34**
2- Social appearance anxiety		1	.36**
3- Self-objectification			1

** $p < 0.01$

Table 1 shows that colorism has a significant positive relationship with SAA and SO ($p < 0.01$) and SAA has a significant positive relationship with SO ($p < 0.01$).

Table 2

Regression Coefficient of Self-Objectification and Colorism on Social Appearance Anxiety among Study Variables (N=243)

Variable	B	B	SE
Self-objectification			
Self-objectification	.62**	.37	.10
Constant	43.65**		1.07
R ²	.138		
Colorism			

Colorism	.326**	.50	.04
Constant	21.81**		2.215
R ²	.25		

** $p < 0.01$

Table 2 shows that colorism positively predicts SAA ($\beta = .50, P < 0.01$) and also that SO predicts SAA ($\beta = .37, P < 0.01$).

Table 3

Mean, Standard Deviation, and T-Values of Males and Females for Self-objectification, colorism, and Social Appearance Anxiety (N = 243)

Variables	Male (n = 121)		Female (n = 122)		t(241)	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
Self-objectification	-5.39	8.51	4.97	8.73	-.386	.700	-2.60	1.75	1.20
Colorism	54.00	22.17	59.35	25.65	-1.73	.083	-11.4	.71	0.22
SAA	39.39	15.45	41.17	15.69	-.887	.376	-5.70	2.16	0.11

Note. SAA = Social Appearance Anxiety

In table 3, it was seen that females exhibit higher scores on SO, colorism, and SAA as compared to males.

Table 4

Mean, Standard Deviation, and T-values of Married and Unmarried for Self-objectification, colorism, and Social Appearance Anxiety (N = 243)

Variables	Married (n = 37)		Unmarried (n = 206)		t(241)	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
Self-Objectification	-4.46	6.64	5.31	8.92	.553	.58	-2.18	3.88	1.24
Colorism	50.29	23.89	57.80	23.97	-1.75	.081	-15.93	.92	0.31
SAA	37.78	15.96	40.72	15.49	-1.05	.29	-8.41	2.53	0.18

Note. SAA = Social Appearance Anxiety

Table 4 showed that unmarried youth exhibit higher scores as compared to married on colorism, SAA and SO

Table 5

ANOVA for Mean Differences of Socio-economic Status and Residence Area on Social Appearance Anxiety (N = 243).

Variable	Lower (n=4)		Middle (n=221)		Upper (n=18)		F(2,240)	η^2	Post hoc
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
SAA	42.00	14.39	40.65	15.46	35.22	16.93	1.039	0.00	1>2>3
	City (n=200)		Village (n=19)		Town (n=24)				
SAA	39.78	15.83	43.76	13.46	41.62	15.01	.65	0.00	1<2>3

Note. SAA = Social Appearance Anxiety

Table 5 shows that youth who belong to lower socioeconomic status exhibited a higher level of SAA as compared to middle and upper socio-economic status. It was also shown that youth belonging to the village exhibited a higher level of SAA as compared to those of the city and town.

Discussion

Colorism is a universal problem that has arisen as a whirlpool. In this study, it was hypothesized that there would be a significant relationship between colorism and SAA. Similar results were produced in a study that

individuals with lower satisfaction with skin color were more anxious regarding their appearance and utilized different tactics of resistance (Boadi, 2017). The findings of this study also revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between SO and SAA. Previous studies have commonly revealed a significant positive relationship between them (Aubrey, 2006; Szymanski & Henning, 2007; Dimas et al., 2021).

According to the results of this study, SO is a predictor of SAA in youth. Similar results were produced in a study that concluded that SO was a predictor of SAA (Tiggemann & Williams, 2012; Tiggemann & Kuring, 2004). It was also hypothesized that Colorism will likely predict SAA in youth. It was evident from past literature that skin color was a significant predictor of appearance evaluation (Falconer & Neville, 2000). In a study, it was revealed that when colorism increases the levels of anxiety and depression also got increased in women (Alexander, 2021). It also came to the surface that colorism significantly predicts psychiatric disorders (Mistry et al., 2021).

It was also hypothesized that females will be more affected by SO, colorism, and SAA as compared to males. The findings of the result revealed that the rate of SO, colorism, and SAA were higher in female than male youth. The results that were derived from this study were similar to the study which claimed that females are more prone to objectification than males, especially in male-centric societies (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997; McKinley, 1998; Vangeel et al., 2018; APA, 2007; Holland et al., 2017; Hughes et al., 2006). Another study suggested that women who face colorism are at risk of developing anxiety levels and other psychological problems (Robinson-Wood, 2014). The symptoms of anxiety normally aren't physical in nature or mood problems but they are more on the somatic side (Brown et al., 1996).

In a study, it was revealed that women scored significantly higher on SO and SAA than men (Tiggemann & Kuring, 2004). Similarly, it was seen that teasing based on appearance was higher in girls compared to boys in childhood and adolescence (Schmidt & Martin, 2019). Another study found that females are more likely to have anxiety disorders than males in life (Bruce et al., 2005). The National Comorbidity Survey (NCS; led from 1990 – 1992) proposed that occurrence rates for lifetime social anxiety disorder were 15.5% for females and 11.1% for men (Kessler et al., 1994).

In a society where marriage is a focal part of cultural aspects (Vaid, 2009), poor convictions concerning dim appearances become a solid reason for having anxiety in females who accept that their skin tone will prevent their chances of getting married. Fair complexion is a necessity to get married in Asia as ladies are continually told across Asia that if they get more obscure, no man will need to wed them (Hundal, 2010). The findings of this study revealed that the rate of SO, colorism, and SAA were higher in unmarried youth. Similar results were found from a study that women are compelled to meet cultural criteria of beauty just so they can have a relationship (Sanchez & Kwang, 2007). A study also showed that 38.3% of males preferred getting married to fair females (Ross, 1997).

It was also seen that women in their mid-twenties scored higher on SAA whereas married ones in their mid-twenties showed lesser scores due to defensive factors related to marriage (Boadi, 2017). Likewise, another study showed higher scores of unmarried on SAA than married ones because they had not found their life partner yet and they were more concerned about their appearance evaluation from the other sex (Ayhan et al., 2021).

In another hypothesis, it was hypothesized that youth who belong to lower socioeconomic status will experience more SAA as compared to other groups. Findings revealed that youth who belong to lower socioeconomic status exhibited a higher level of SAA as compared to middle and upper socioeconomic status ones. Similar results were seen in a study that claimed that people who have social anxiety usually have low socioeconomic status (Stein et al., 1994). It was highlighted that people with low socioeconomic status have more levels of SAA as compared to those with higher financial status. It was then stated that higher socioeconomic status could act as a protective factor for the development of any psychopathology as the ones with lower socioeconomic status are more prone to psychopathology (Özcan et al., 2013). Another study showed similar results that financial status has a significant effect on a person's appearance and attitudes (Osman & Bozgeya, 2015). The National Epidemiologic Survey (2002) revealed that being young and having low socioeconomic status may set you at risk of having social anxiety disorder (Grant et al., 2005).

In the last hypothesis, it was hypothesized that youth who belongs to the village will have more SAA as compared to others. The findings of the result revealed that youth who belong to the village exhibited a higher level of SAA as compared to those who belong to the city and town. Similar results were seen in a study that claimed that SAA was higher in women who were living in rural areas (George et al., 1986). Jefferies & Ungar (2020) noted that those living in urban areas scored lower on the SAA as compared to those who belong to rural

areas. Osman & Bozgeyā (2015) reported that the level of the SAA in youth belonging to cities was significantly lower as compared to those living in rural areas. Waghachavare et al. (2014) also reported that anxiety related to body image was mostly prevalent in individuals belonging to rural areas which was the main factor in developing a social anxiety disorder. Another study also showed that 24.5 % of women belonging to rural areas had dissatisfaction with their body image leading to social anxiety (Dixit et al., 2011).

Limitations, Future Directions and Conclusions

The data collection was difficult as the data was collected online amid covid-19. It is suggested that in future studies, a large sample from various populations should be taken so the results could be more generalizable. It is recommended that qualitative data should be collected with quantitative data. More research studies should be done to explore different factors and their impact of them on our culture as there are very less studies conducted on these variables in Pakistan. This research will help in raising awareness about the risk factors that emerge due to colorism and SO to rectify this fallacy of our culture about beauty and glamour. This will help us to eradicate our own biases and inclinations towards beauty and cultural standards which could create potential threats to psychological health. It will help mental health professionals in developing intervention or counseling plans for those who had a significant impact of these factors in their life. This study will provide awareness regarding the prevalence of these issues among the normal population to not evaluate students based on skin color as this is unquestionably unfair.

It is concluded that in Pakistan, the concepts of seeing the darker individual as inferior are prevalent and deeply rooted in our society and we barely notice it. Similarly, the bias towards the perfect body has raised the SO in our youth causing numerous physical or psychological health issues including SAA. Colorism and SO are not new phenomena worldwide but we as a society have failed to consider them as an arising problematic issue. According to the findings of this study, these variables have a greater impact on the youth of Pakistan and hence rates of SAA are increasing at large. Mental health practitioners could use to results of this current study in the future to explore more constructs related to these variables as there are limited indigenous researches available on the variables.

Disclosure Statement

All authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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